

Halocobaloximes containing axially coordinated imidazole or histidine : Microwave assisted synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity

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Abstract : The complexes of the type *trans*-[Co(dmgh)₂(L)X] where dmgh⁻ = dimethylglyoximate, L = imidazole (Imi) or histidine (His) and X⁻ = Cl⁻, Br⁻ or I⁻ were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, TG/DTA, FABMS, UV-Visible, IR and ¹H NMR spectra. The FABMS analysis confirmed the expected molecular weight for the complexes. The thermal analysis of the complexes reveals that the bromo complexes dissociate at higher temperatures compared to the chloro complexes, the iodo cobaloximes being unstable even at low temperature decomposing without any sharp change in mass. The free ligands viz. dmgh₂, Imi and His showed no antibacterial activity against the bacteria tested but, cobaloximes were found to be active against most of the microbes. Iodocobaloximes were found to be more active than the corresponding chloro- and bromo-cobaloximes with the antibacterial activity order for the axial halides as I⁻ > Cl⁻ > Br⁻ and that of the axial nitrogen heterocycles as histidine > imidazole.

Keywords : Cobalt(III) complexes, cobaloximes, imidazole, histidine.

Introduction

For decades together, cobaloximes have been the standing model for vitamin-B₁₂. The urge to explore modification in such vitamin-B₁₂ model leads way to the investigation of simple models containing cobalamines¹. Metal complexes containing nitrogen and sulphur donor atoms have been proved to be potential antibacterials as well as good fungicides². Cobalt carbonyls were found to show anti tumour activity *in vivo*³. Satyanarayana *et al.*⁴, have studied the protonation equilibria of alkyl cobaloximes containing heterocyclic nitrogen donors.

Amino acids provide an excellent path to explore the field of medicinal chemistry. Imidazole, the heterocyclic moiety of the amino acid histidine has set its eminence in the field of biological and coordination chemistry not only due to its ambidentate ligation⁵, but also to the various role played by its derivatives in the field of pharmacology⁶. Histidine in heme plays an important role in the metabolic activities, it is also one of the major ultraviolet absorbing complexes in the skin.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Cobalt(II) halides (purchased from SD Research Laboratory) SISCO, sample of dimethyl glyoxime and HI Pure samples of imidazole and histidine were used for the preparations of the complexes. Dimethyl sulphoxide (SD Research Laboratory) was dried over calcium hydride and distilled fractionally at reduced pressure. The distilled solvent, stored under molecular sieves, was used for the study of the antibacterial activity.

Preparation of the cobaloximes :

Preparation of dihalo cobaloximes :

Cobalt(II) halide (CoCl₂·6H₂O or CoBr₂·6H₂O) was intimately grinded and exposed to microwave for 60 s. The dehydrated cobalt(II) halide was mixed with dimethylglyoxime in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The mixture was stirred for about an hour in acetone to get green complexes of the type H[Co(dmgh)₂X₂] where X = Cl⁻ or Br⁻.

The dichloro cobaloxime, H[Co(dmgh)₂Cl₂] synthesized above was mixed with water and exposed

Note

to microwave for 60 s. The light brown complex aquochlorocobaloxime, $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ was filtered and mixed with equimolar proportion of potassium iodide and exposed to microwave for 60 s. The brown colored aquoiodocobaloxime, $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{I}]$ thus obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether.

Preparation of cobaloximes containing nitrogen heterocycles :

The dichloro-, dibromo- and aquoiodocobaloximes synthesized above were mixed with imidazole or histidine in 1 : 1 ratio in ethanol and refluxed for 2 to 3 h to get light brown colored complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{L})\text{X}]$ where L = imidazole (Imi) or histidine (His) and $\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-$ or Br^- , whereas aquoiodocobaloxime was mixed with imidazole or histidine in 1 : 1 ratio in water and refluxed for 2 to 3 h to get dark brown colored complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{L})\text{I}]$.

Characterisation of the complexes :

All the complexes were characterized by elemental analysis and FABMS (CDRI, Lucknow). The UV-Visible spectra were recorded on LAMBDA-125 spectrophotometer in ethanol using matched quartz cells of path length 1 cm. The IR spectra of complexes were obtained on KBr pellet on Perkin-Elmer IR spectrum-1 spectrophotometer and the ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ using JOEL 400 MHz NMR spectrophotometer. The TG/DTA was obtained on Perkin-Elmer Model Pyris Diamond at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ purged with argon gas at the rate of 12 L h^{-1} .

Preparation of test organisms :

The bacterial strains such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 441) and the other strains of gram-negative bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 15380), *Vibrio fischeri* (1738), *Yersinia amylovora* (ATCC 2760), *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* (MTCC 451), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Yersinia enterocolitica* (840), *Enterobacter aerogens* (MTCC 111), *Proteus vulgaris* (ATCC 1771). Methiciline resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *Escherichia coli* Cipro R (ICMR-24), *Acetobacter baumannii* (Carbapenum R) were used for

the study of antibacterial activity. All the strains were obtained from the Department of Microbiology, Christian Medical College, Vellore, India. The bacterial and fungal stocks were maintained in MHA slants stored at $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Antibacterial activity test :

Antibacterial activity was tested using a minimum modification of the disc diffusion method originally described by Bauer *et al.*⁷. The complexes were dissolved in 20% DMSO in water. The inoculums for each microorganism were prepared from broth cultures (10^5 CFU/ml). A loop of culture from the MHA slant stock was cultured in Muller Hinton broth overnight and spread with a sterile cotton swab into petri plates containing 15 ml MHA. Sterile Hi-media disc (6 mm in diameter) impregnated with the complexes (250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$, 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$, 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$) were placed on the cultured plates and incubated for 24 h at $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The solvent without the complexes served as negative control. Standard antibiotics of streptomycin (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$) was used as positive controls. The results were recorded by measuring the zones of growth inhibition surrounding the disc zone scale (Hi media). Clear inhibition zones around the discs indicated the presence of antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

Ramesh *et al.*⁸ have reported the X-ray single crystal structure of dichloro cobaloxime. Dichloro- and dibromo-cobaloximes are intense green crystalline complexes which change their color to brown after the addition of one mole of heterocyclic donors like pyridine and its derivatives⁹. A similar color change with heterocyclic ligands imidazole or histidine shows that their reactivity towards dihalocobaloximes is similar to that of other heterocyclic ligands.

Elemental analysis :

The elemental data obtained by analytical methods agree well with the theoretical data (Found : C, 34.05; H, 4.52; N, 19.85. Calcd. for $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{His})\text{Cl}]$: C, 35.03; H, 4.80; N, 20.43% and Found : C, 32.99; H, 4.56; N, 20.98. Calcd. for $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{Imi})\text{Cl}]$: C, 33.62; H, 4.60, N, 21.40%). The elemental data for the bromo and iodo complexes were also found to be in good agreement with the calculated values.

FABMS :

The FABMS analysis confirmed the expected molecular weight for the complexes with the corresponding molecular ion peaks for $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{His})\text{Cl}]$ at m/z 479 and for $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{Imi})\text{Cl}]$ at m/z 392.

UV-Visible spectra :

The UV spectrum of cobaloximes containing imidazole and histidine show an absorption around 220 nm which may be attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the imidazole or histidine which remains unchanged in their complexes. The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition occurs around 280 nm. The less intense peak in the range 280–350 nm may be due to $d-d$ transition of low spin d^6 cobalt(III) viz. ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ with the other high energy spin allowed $d-d$ transition viz. ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ at 570 nm.

IR spectra :

Navaneetha *et al.*¹⁰ have reported the stretching and bending frequencies for the complexes containing imidazole and histidine. The C=N stretching vibration of oxime in its complexes was observed in the range 1550–1600 cm^{-1} and the intermolecular hydrogen bonded -OH at 3400 cm^{-1} . A moderate peak around 1340 cm^{-1} , observed for all the complexes may be assigned to the =N-O- stretching of the oxime. The peak at 520 cm^{-1} could be attributed to Co-N stretching.

TG-DTA studies :

The thermal studies of the cobalt(III) complexes reveal that the axial halogen dissociates first followed by the dissociation of the heterocyclic nitrogen donor viz. imidazole or histidine as reported by Nayak *et al.*¹¹. In the case of chloro complexes a sharp peak was observed at about 165 °C due to the dissociation of Cl⁻ followed by continuous dissociation of histidine (225 °C). The dissociation of bromo complexes occurred at higher temperatures compared to the chloro complexes. The dissociation of Br⁻ occurred at 225 °C followed by the dissociation of histidine at 240 °C and dmgh at moderately higher temperature (275 °C). The iodo cobaloximes were found to be unstable even at low temperature decomposing from 210 °C without any sharp mass change.

¹H NMR :

The interaction between equatorial and axial ligands in cobaloximes were analysed by earlier workers^{12,13}.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes show an intense peak at δ 1.9 to 2.3 ppm (12H) characteristic of methyl group of dimethylglyoxime and a multiplet in the range δ 6.3 to 7.9 ppm supports the presence of the axial histidine or imidazole.

Antibacterial activity studies :

Cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes were found to be active against some microbes^{14,15} and drug resistant pathogen *Acetobacter baumannii* (ICMR-19) which is *Carbapenem* resistant for which no activity was observed with standard (Streptomycin). But in the present study $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{His})\text{Cl}]$ shows only moderate activity and $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{Imi})\text{Cl}]$ does not show any activity towards the reference cultures, whereas the complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{His})\text{Br}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2(\text{His})\text{I}]$ were found to show medium activity. The iodo cobaloximes were found to be more active than the chloro and bromo cobaloximes. Cobaloximes containing histidine were found to be more active against the microbes compared to its heterocyclic moiety imidazole. The high antibacterial activity of iodocobaloximes can be attributed to high polarisability of the iodide ions. The basic nature of histidine and the zwitter ionic character of amino acid (histidine) play a strong role in expanding cell walls of the pathogens considered. The active sites of the pathogens are very well captured by the amino acid histidine than its heterocyclic moiety due to the absence of such pH variations in imidazole.

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